

ALIKHAN BOKEIKHAN AND ALASH ORDA: THE PHENOMENON OF NATIONAL STATE-BUILDING

KURALAY ASHEKEYEVA

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Associate Professor, Candidate of Philosophical Sciences
Almaty, Kazakhstan

NURSHARKHAN ASHEKEYEVA

Ilias Zhansugurov Zhetysu State University, Associate Professor, Candidate of Political Sciences
Taldykorgan, Kazakhstan

Abstract. *The article examines the phenomenon of national state-building led by Alikhan Bokeikhan in the Alash movement and the Alash-Orda government. It analyzes the programmatic documents of Alash-Orda, resistance to the Bolsheviks, the land issue, and Alikhan's role in the Shcherbina expedition. Using comparative and structural-functional methods, it demonstrates the reliance of Alash on principles of national unity and democracy, as well as the influence of these ideas on modern state-building in Kazakhstan.*

Keywords: *Alash-Orda, national autonomy, land issue, Shcherbina expedition, resistance to Bolsheviks, national unity, state-building, Alash party.*

The Alash Party and the Alash Orda government, led by Alikhan Bokeikhan, relied on the principles of national unity and popular solidarity in determining ways to resolve socio-political, socio-economic, and national state-building issues in Kazakhstan. This position was diametrically opposed to the Bolshevik views based on class struggle and the dictatorship of the proletariat. Consequently, Alash Orda did not endorse the October Revolution or Soviet power and actively opposed them. This article analyzes Alikhan Bokeikhan's political and social ideas regarding national state-building using comparative and structural-functional methods.

In Chapter I of the Alash Party program, titled "State Structure," it is stated: "Russia shall be a democratic, federative republic. At the head of the government shall be a president elected annually according to the decision of the Constituent Assembly and the State Duma. The president shall govern the people through ministers, and these ministers shall be accountable to the Constituent Assembly and the State Duma. Deputies shall be elected by universal, equal, direct, and secret ballot. In matters of suffrage, there shall be no discrimination based on class, religion, or gender. Laws shall be enacted solely by the State Duma, and the Duma shall have the right to oversee the government, conduct audits, and submit inquiries. State taxes shall not be imposed by the Duma" [1, p. 220]. This program demonstrates support for Russia's federative structure and democratic principles.

The delimitation of Alash autonomy's borders was interrupted due to the events of the Civil War. Statements by A. Bokeikhan and other leaders did not explicitly mention the creation of an independent Kazakh state, but their goal was to achieve national autonomy.

The second direction in establishing Kazakh autonomy was the Bolshevik approach to the national question: granting autonomy to the nationalities inhabiting Russia and creating a Soviet national statehood. Upon returning from emigration, the Bolshevik leader emphasized that, in a multinational state, the program's key issues included the right to secession and the proposal of local (national) autonomy [2, p. 33]. Half a year later, when the Bolsheviks came to power, implementing this became a priority on the agenda.

In the appeal of the Council of People's Commissars of the RSFSR dated November 20, 1917, "To the Muslims of Russia and the East," it specifically mentioned "the Kyrgyz and Sarts of Siberia and

Turkestan,” which contained an inaccuracy, as there were no Sarts in Siberia [3, p. 210]. However, Petrograd was well aware of the presence of Kazakhs in both Siberia and Turkestan.

One of the first representatives of Russia’s peoples received by the Chairman of the Council of People’s Commissars was Alibi Zhangeldin, who had been a Bolshevik since 1915. In Zhangeldin’s memoirs, he describes meeting Ya. M. Sverdlov in Petrograd and being told that an appointment for party work required discussion with V. I. Lenin. He then went to the Smolny Institute and met Lenin. Lenin highlighted that the Bolshevik program aimed to liberate oppressed peoples, create conditions for their independent development, and attract the intelligentsia to their side. He tasked Zhangeldin with defending the slogan “All Power to the Soviets!” and appointed him Extraordinary Military Commissar of Torgai Region [4, p. 25]. V. I. Lenin signed Zhangeldin’s credentials as temporary extraordinary commissar of Torgai Region on December 13, 1917. Thus, the Bolshevik Zhangeldin took control of Torgai Region, where Alikhan Bokeikhan had previously served as commissar.

Telegrams began arriving in Petrograd from Kazakh supporters of Soviet power expressing disagreement with the decisions of the Second All-Kazakh Congress. On December 16, 1917, a mass rally in Akmola adopted a resolution recognizing the new government. Soviet power in Akmola reported to the People’s Commissariat for Nationalities of the RSFSR, stating its disapproval of Alash Orda [5, p. 61]. The Third All-Russian Congress of Soviets on January 15, 1918, endorsed the Leninist principle of nations’ self-determination. National policy became state policy. The first principle of a federative republic—the Soviet principle—implied a federation formed on national-territorial grounds [6, p. 28].

In Western Siberia, Soviet power was established later than in Russia’s central regions. It was formalized at the Third Western Siberian Congress of Soviets held in Omsk from December 2–10, 1917. The victory of the new government was achieved with the help of Omsk and other guard detachments in Petropavl and other cities of Kazakhstan. In Omsk, the “Kyrgyz Socialist Party” (“Ush Zhuz”) was formed in opposition to the Alash Party. It supported Soviet power and aimed to establish a national-bourgeois autonomy. In April 1918, the chairman of “Ush Zhuz,” Kolbai Togosov, sent a telegram to V. I. Lenin, Chairman of the Council of People’s Commissars [7, p. 67].

Representatives of Alash Orda, led by Alikhan Bokeikhan, raised the issue of granting autonomy to the Kyrgyz Steppe Region. However, this demand was not satisfied; it was stated that autonomy for the “Kyrgyzes” should have socialist content within the framework of Soviet construction. V. I. Lenin declared that the Council of People’s Commissars would approve Kazakh autonomy only on a Soviet basis [8, p. 45]. In April 1918, the People’s Commissar for Nationalities considered, among his first issues, the autonomies of “Kyrgyz regions” and “Turkestan and Tatar-Bashkir.” Government documents indicated that “autonomy in Kyrgyz territory is being planned.” This referred not only to the full unity of “Kyrgyz” territory but also to undetermined Kazakh districts. In 1918, V. I. Lenin received A. Zhangeldin and issued him a mandate as Extraordinary Commissar of the Steppe Region. Subsequently, Zhangeldin sent telegrams to Akmola and Semipalatinsk regions requesting unification into a single Kyrgyz region [9, p. 105].

In the “Bulletins of the All-Russian Central Executive Committee” on May 12, 1918, a decree of the Council of People’s Commissars of the RSFSR was published on establishing a Kyrgyz Section within the People’s Commissariat for Nationalities to prepare the state structure of the Kyrgyz Region. The Kyrgyz Section was tasked with developing an administrative-territorial project for the future national autonomy. By this time, the foundations of the Soviet administrative-territorial structure had been determined. Primarily, historical and economic conditions were taken into account when establishing administrative borders, and the placement of state apparatus close to the population was planned. In May 1918, a decree “On Changing Borders” was issued, followed by acts of the NKVD. One of these acts stated that each settlement, volost, or uezd had the opportunity to join the natural center it preferred [10, p. 38]. Thus, the need arose to discuss a convenient transition to the new administrative-territorial division, taking into account the opinions of nationalities promised autonomy.

The Civil War hindered the granting of autonomy and the creation of a new administrative-territorial structure in the regions inhabited by the nomadic Kazakh population. Alash members found themselves in the White Guard camp. On June 24, 1918, Alikhan Bokeikhan, as Chairman of Alash Orda, signed a resolution annulling all decrees of Soviet power and military Soviet organizations in the Kyrgyz steppe territory and called on “young men to fight the Bolsheviks.”

The White Guards had no intention of granting any autonomy to the Kazakhs. One of their slogans against Soviet power was “For a United and Indivisible Russia.” In the summer of 1918, the Minister of War of the Provisional Siberian Government, Major General P. P. Ivanov-Rinov, declared that “non-Russians must be held in iron gauntlets” (“Inorodtsy nado derzhat’ v ezhovykh rukavitsakh”) [11, p. 5]. Under Admiral Kolchak’s dictatorship, attitudes toward “non-Russians” hardened further; Kazakhs faced repression and imprisonment. The editor of *Saryarka*, I. Alimbekov, was also jailed, as was Zhakyp Akbaev, chairman of the Kazakh court for civil affairs in Semipalatinsk. They were accused of supporting the Bolsheviks. Imam Alimbekov was charged with illegally possessing weapons, having ties to underground organizations, and distributing leaflets against the Kolchak government [12, p. 266]. The organ of the right-wing Kadets in Semipalatinsk, the newspaper *Svobodnaya Rech*, attempted to discredit Alash Orda leader Alikhan Bokeikhan before the Kolchak government: “We heard that Sultan Bokeikhanov is to be appointed representative administering the Kyrgyz region... Bokeikhanov does not represent the will of the entire Kyrgyz people; he is merely a leader defending the interests of a specific group within the Kyrgyz intelligentsia. Therefore, appointing Mr. Bokeikhanov as representative of the Kyrgyz people would be akin to entrusting their fate to a ravenous wolf” [13, p. 209].

Such conclusions demonstrate an underestimation of A. Bokeikhan’s political foresight and leadership qualities. In reality, Bokeikhan had timely reformed his views. In his article “Why Did I Leave the Kadet Party?” he wrote: “The Kadet Party considers it acceptable for land to become private property. The Kadet Party opposes autonomy. We, under the Alash banner, gathered to establish national autonomy... To improve the affairs of the Kazakh-Kyrgyz, it would be better to separate them from government affairs. In Russian, this is called ‘otdelenie tserkvi ot gosudarstva’ (separation of church and state). The Kadet Party views my opinion differently. These three divergences became clear this year. Afterward, I sought to create the Alash Party for the Kazakhs. I stated this at the general Kazakh congress in July” [11, p. 414]. This resolute decision marks him as a statesman who thought at the national level, resolved socio-political issues based on principles of popular unity, and aimed to join the ranks of civilized nations. Ideologically, he was close to the Russian Kadet Party (Constitutional Democrats)—the Party of People’s Freedom. Kazakh intellectuals were attracted to the Kadets’ ideas of democratizing state structure, the right of each nation in Russia to self-determination, and implementing legal order and rule of law.

In 1905, a congress of delegates from five regions was held in Uralsk with the participation of Bokeikhan, Seidalin, Tynyshpaev, Syrtanov, and other Kazakh intellectuals, where a decision was made to establish a “Kazakh Constitutional-Democratic Party.” A similar congress took place in Semipalatinsk in 1906. Overall, the emergence of the Alash Party can be attributed to two reasons: the need to fight colonial tsarist policy and the demand to transform patriarchal-feudal social relations in the steppe. Therefore, national liberation and liberal-bourgeois orientations formed the party’s primary characteristics. In terms of its social base, it qualifies as a people’s party.

The Kazakh intellectuals led by A. Bokeikhan took an anti-Bolshevik stance. They recognized that the October Revolution was unnecessary for Kazakhstan. Perceiving that Soviet power’s actions constituted a new form of colonial policy, they opposed it decisively. Against the Bolsheviks, who relied on class principles and the dictatorship of the proletariat, Alash Orda upheld national unity and popular solidarity.

After the October Revolution’s victory, in the appeal “To All Muslim Toilers of Russia and the East,” Soviet power promised a fair resolution of the national question. The Second All-Russian

Congress of Soviets declared in its appeal to the people: “It ensures the gratuitous transfer of landlord, appanage, and monastery lands to peasant committees; implements full democratization of the army and protects soldiers’ rights; establishes workers’ control over production; ensures timely convocation of the Constituent Assembly; and cares for the delivery of essential goods to cities and villages” [1, p. 134]. This gained support from toilers who had borne heavy burdens in World War I.

Alash Orda distrusted the Provisional Government, which failed to resolve critical issues such as national state-building, land, resettlement, and violence by Kazakh-Russian troops. It boldly opposed Soviet power, which sought to address these on class principles. It rejected Kazakh statehood on a Soviet basis. History has shown that the Bolshevik program led even Russia itself into a deadlock.

It was considered that Kazakhstan was far removed from Russia’s class stratification. Alash leaders understood that, for a people under colonial oppression like the Kazakhs, uniting on the basis of common national interests was more appropriate than class division at that time. Alikhan Bokeikhan called for unity: “If we sit idly, we will be lost among the fingers. The Kazakh people must take care of their own affairs. Storm at the front door, enemy at the back. Sons of Alash, after the Great Calamity and Great Flight, in 200 years a grave matter has come upon you. Elder brothers and young heroes, set aside family feuds and disputes, unite and serve the people!” [11, p. 298]. He also urged solidarity: “The Russian state will not soon join the herd. If we lose unity, we will wander like Russians. Leading elders and educated youth, fulfill local duties honestly. Lead the entire people” [11, p. 298].

The “Russian” or “Muslim” question was never a pure issue. The core issue was power. From the outset, the Bolshevik regime skillfully directed the ambitious intentions of open and potential opponents to its advantage. National peculiarities, historical experience, oppositional programs, and leaders’ personal abilities were taken into account.

In A. Bokeikhan’s articles, Alash Orda’s position on the land issue can be systematized as follows:

- In Kazakh autonomy, the influx of settlers must be halted until landless Kazakh masses receive land. Land shares should first go to local populations displaced from ancestral lands during tsarist times;
- In all regions and districts, land shares and norms shall be determined by local land committees;
- When allocating land to Kazakhs, it shall be divided according to villages, clans, tribes, or their own wishes. Tribes, villages, or volosts receiving land together shall establish internal order and use it justly;
- Nominal special rights of Kazakhs to land shall be abolished forever. Local populations shall receive land from their ancestral territories;
- Sale of land is prohibited;
- The surface resources, waters, and subsurface minerals of Alash autonomy territory shall be Alash property.

Implementing such ambitious tasks was only possible for a government based on the demands and lifestyles of approximately 5 million Kazakhs and other peoples. National peculiarities must be considered. Only a national council elected by the people themselves can determine each nation’s way of life.

Regarding the status of Alash Orda autonomy, I. Stalin’s opinion was as follows: “The well-known resolution issued by the People’s Commissars on the rights of Russia’s peoples remains the foundation of Soviet government’s work on the national question to this day. The Third Congress of Soviets resolved to implement this resolution. The resolution of the general Kazakh-Kyrgyz congress submitted to us fully corresponds to the above. However, we set one condition: provided that your congress’s resolution and representatives do not oppose recognition of Soviet power. The Third Congress of Soviets resolved to draft a law on Soviet federation and submit it for approval by the Congress of Soviets. In light of this, it is time to stop talking and start acting—that is, peoples with different lifestyles and customs should unite with local Soviets to form commissions for convening congresses to realize national aspirations such as autonomy, federation, or outright separation. We believe that the representatives of the general Kazakh-

Kyrgyz will promptly prepare and, without missing the opportune moment, unite with local Soviets to form such a commission. We request that you submit our proposal to the Alash Orda Council and provide a response. Address: Moscow, Kremlin, to the Chairman of the Council of People's Commissars Lenin and People's Commissar Stalin. People's Commissar for Nationalities Stalin" [14, p. 29].

The key point in Stalin's statement is his acknowledgment that the general Kazakh-Kyrgyz congress resolution aligns with the Declaration on the Rights of the Peoples of Russia. This alignment provided grounds for Soviet power to recognize Alash Orda, with the sole condition being Alash Orda's recognition of Soviet power. Following negotiations with Stalin, the Alash Orda Council discussed the center's proposal and adopted the following decision:

"On March 21, 1918, after reviewing the words of the People's Commissar for Nationalities Stalin on Alash autonomy, the members of Alash Orda resolved to recognize Soviet power as the central authority for all autonomous peoples in Russia and declared the following:

1. In accordance with the resolution of the general Kazakh-Kyrgyz congress held in Orenburg from December 5–13, the regions unconditionally included in Alash autonomy: Semipalatinsk, Akmola, Torgai, Ural, Syrdarya, Ferghana, Zhetysu, Bokei Horde, Mangystau uezd of Transcaspian Region, Jizzakh uezd of Samarkand Region, and Kazakhs in Amu Darya, Barnaul, and Zmeinogorsk uezds.

2. Per the congress resolution, ten persons from non-Kazakh peoples—proportionally more or less—shall be elected to Alash Orda.

3. In Alash autonomy, legislative and governing power shall belong to Alash Orda.

4. The authority to convene the Constituent Assembly shall rest with Alash Orda; regional Soviets shall assist.

5. Power in regions and uezds under Alash shall reside in Soviets of deputies elected by Kazakhs and peasants proportionally; power in cities shall reside in Soviets elected by urban residents, workers, and soldiers.

6. Until the general population elects Soviets proportionally, regional and uezd Kazakh committees and city dumas shall continue managing people's affairs and education in their previous form.

7. Kazakhs and Kyrgyzes shall resolve internal matters through regional and uezd courts they themselves elect.

8. Per our congress resolution, a militia shall be established among Kazakh-Kyrgyzes.

9. Members of Alash Orda's education commission, Kazakh committees, and Zemstvo administrations arrested by order of local Soviets and held in prison shall be released immediately, and henceforth persecution based on false complaints shall cease.

10. Alash Orda members and Zhahansha Dosmukhamedov are appointed as representatives to Soviet power on Kazakh-Kyrgyz affairs. (Khaled and Zhahansha are currently in Moscow negotiating autonomy on behalf of Alash Orda.)

11. Soviet power shall review Alash Orda's above conditions and respond promptly.

After hearing all conditions, People's Commissar Stalin promised a direct telegraphic verbal response without delay."

In the prolonged maneuvering with Kazakh nationalists, the regime primarily used leaders under the pretext of creating preconditions for reviving political and economic reforms in Soviet territories. The factor of combating "great-power chauvinism" was introduced to remove former administration representatives from power and establish direct central control. By admitting bourgeois liberals into the party, they kept them close while enabling surveillance of "unreliable comrades." After the overthrow of tsarist power, Alash intellectuals who defined the national orientation immediately took up establishing national autonomy. A. Bokeikhan emphasized the need for future political unity: "If we sit idly, we will be lost among the fingers. The Kazakh people must take care of their own affairs. Storm at the front door, enemy at the back. Sons of Alash, after the Great Calamity and Great Flight, in 200 years a grave matter

has come upon you. Elders and young heroes, set aside family feuds and disputes, unite and serve the people!”

In the Alash Party program, the section “Local Freedom” states: “All regions inhabited by Kazakhs shall unite with self-governance and become a federative member of the Russian Republic. If circumstances allow, Kazakh autonomy may temporarily unite with allied peoples; if not, it may become fully independent. In any case, current zemstvo institutions shall be adopted.” The “Land Issue” section specifies: “Lands of Akmola, Semipalatinsk, Torgai, Transcaspian, Zhetysu, Syrdarya regions, Bokei Governorate, and other areas inhabited by Kazakhs shall enter the composition of Alash autonomy” [15, p. 94].

In his article “The Fourth Duma and the Kazakh,” Alikhan Bokeikhan noted during budget discussions that an orphaned people like the Kazakhs speak only once a year [17, p. 298]. For example, Siberian deputies had been complaining for seven years since the Third Duma about taking good Kazakh lands, while Kazakhs themselves began migrating elsewhere as settlers. He openly proposed that settled lands of indigenous Buryats and Kazakhs should have been given to settlers first and criticized the government for not yet introducing a law to settle inhabited lands [17, p. 298].

The Temporary Regulations of 1867–1868 included norms converting Kazakh community lands into state property. From the late 19th century, lands were seized for cities and railways. Under the agrarian reform led by P. Stolypin, Chairman of the Council of Ministers, Kazakh lands were confiscated, deepening tsarist colonial policy. The reform aimed to dissolve peasant communes and create strong independent farms. Stolypin sought to expand land at the expense of “treasury” lands in Siberia and Kazakhstan without touching large landlord estates. On June 10, 1903, the “Regulation on Voluntary Settlement on Treasury Lands in Syrdarya, Ferghana, and Samarkand Regions” was adopted, providing for taking “surplus” lands from locals. On June 25, 1903, the “Regulation on Government Assistance to Settlers in Siberia and the Steppe General-Governorship” defined benefits for peasant settlers. In 1904, a Resettlement Administration was established, which “identified” surplus lands, confiscated them from Kazakhs, and created a resettlement fund to allocate plots to settlers. Stolypin’s decree of November 9, 1906, on transferring peasants from communes to khutors was confirmed by law on June 14, 1910, increasing the number of settlers in Kazakhstan.

As a result of resettlement policy from Russia’s central governorates to Kazakhstan between 1897 and 1916, 1,301,000 peasants were relocated, drastically altering the demographic situation. By 1917, the Russian and Ukrainian population reached 56% in Akmola Region, 22% in Semipalatinsk, 38% in Torgai, 14% in Ural, and 22% in Zhetysu. The seizure of Kazakh lands fueled the rise of the national liberation movement [18, p. 20].

Alikhan Bokeikhan considered the land issue and territorial integrity paramount in defining socio-economic problems. As a forestry specialist and economist-scholar, he was one of the few deeply researching the Kazakh people’s way of life, economy, culture, lands, waters, and socio-economic conditions. From 1896, Alikhan focused on scientific work. Before the Shcherbina Expedition, A. Bokeikhan participated in census work in Tobol Governorate, gaining experience. Initially invited to the Shcherbina Expedition as a statistician, he later led an independent research team. The expedition’s main goal was comprehensive study of the Kazakh steppe, which had become an object of Russia’s resettlement policy since the 1890s.

This involved determining the scale of Kazakh households, summer and winter pastures, arable and hay lands, and accounting for Kazakh lands, waters, forests, and deserts. Alikhan directly participated in work in Pavlodar, Karkaraly, and Semipalatinsk uezds of Semipalatinsk Region and Omsk uezd of Akmola Region, collecting diverse factual material. He counted households and livestock. After the expedition, he selected and processed the collected material, wrote scientific conclusions, prepared necessary tables, and drew land and water maps. He provided scientific descriptions of Kazakh economy, arable and hay lands, and winter-summer pastures. Based on the data, he identified “primary historical

districts” in Pavlodar, Karkaraly, Semipalatinsk, and Omsk uezds and mapped them. He calculated the economic efficiency of Kazakh farming.

Using materials from these four uezds, Alikhan Bokeikhan also examined the issue of Kazakh land community. It is known that each Kazakh tribe and clan had its own habitat, winter-summer pastures, and rivers. From this, Alikhan deeply studied the tribal-clan structure of Kazakh society, compiled genealogies of Kazakh clans, marked their steppe habitats and lands on maps. He also studied the economy of settlers from Russia’s internal governorates in the four uezds, noting the inefficiency of their arable farming. Relying on expedition results, he consistently opposed Russian resettlement policy. The expedition’s findings were published in 13 volumes between 1903 and 1905. Alikhan’s work in the Shcherbina Expedition demonstrated his comprehensive scientific preparation, profound knowledge, and love for his native land.

The Alash movement represents a crucial stage in forming Kazakhstan’s national statehood. Under Alikhan Bokeikhan’s leadership, principles of national unity and democracy were foundational. Opposition to the Bolsheviks stemmed from differences in class and national perspectives. The land issue formed the basis of socio-economic reforms. The Alash Orda phenomenon laid the foundation for Kazakh statehood, but the Civil War and political pressures prevented its full realization.

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